

Milestone: M3.5 The B1MG data analysis challenge results

Lead Participant: CRG

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Due: 30 Nov 2022

Date Of Completion: 20 Oct 2023

Means of Verification

Deliverable D3.3 The B1MG data analysis challenge

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes
Significant delays were incurred due to the lengthy process of drafting an MTA for the materials analyzed. Also, the huge amounts of data used made the file transfers extremely long and difficult, as well as posed serious informatic problems to process the data.

Project participants & others

CGSTHLM (Sweden), CNAG (SPAIN), DNGC-CPH (Denmark), DKFZ (Germany), FIMM (Finland), HARTWIG (Netherlands), MOMA (Denmark), OUH (Norway), University of VERONA (Italy)

Next action steps

- For future benchmarks, we will test beforehand the participants' infrastructure for receiving and handling large amounts of data
- Manual curation of the challenging somatic variants identified
- Finalising the goldsets and lab performance comparisons
- Drafting of final reports

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